

Youth Character Development and Teacher-Parent Partnership: A Systematic Literature Review

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ABSTRACT

Background: Collaboration between teachers and parents is essential in the growing years of youth since it helps them build character, such as a sense of responsibility or empathy. Still, difficulties like different strategies and time constraints can affect communication.

Objective: This research aims to analyse how parents' and teachers' involvement in fostering adolescent character forms, including supporting and inhibiting factors.

Methodology: This research uses a qualitative approach with a Systematic Literature Review (SLR) and PRISMA analysis. Some database searches were conducted using English search terms. This review included nine articles.

Result: It was found that various efforts and forms of teacher-parent partnerships, such as parent-teacher meetings, socialisation programmes, communication, and others, are involved in adolescent character development, as well as things that support and hinder these partnerships.

Conclusion: Various efforts are made between teachers and parents in fostering adolescent character; various forms of cooperation maximise supporting factors and minimise inhibiting factors for cooperation between teachers and parents in fostering adolescent character.

Unique Contribution: This research opens up various opportunities for further studies on adolescent character development through cooperation between teachers and parents.

Key recommendation: To minimise inhibiting factors while maximising supporting factors for teacher-parent partnerships, it is necessary to expand innovative strategies to strengthen teacher-parent partnerships in developing adolescent character.

Keywords: partnership; teacher-parent; character; adolescent

Introduction

The relationship between teachers and parents regarding the formation of teenage characters is an acute problem in modern education. Many studies prove the benefit of this cooperation on adult character formation (Deng et al., 2018; Zhu et al., 2022). Values like responsibility, integrity, and empathy are easier to teach and implement in the daily behaviours of adolescents with effective cooperation. In this case, the teacher and parents must know their goals about character education that will be developed methods to achieve these goals (Harrison et al., 2022; Ritonga, 2022; Mukminin & Habibi, 2019).

Adolescent character education in school is practically the main topic of this editorial. In addition to the academic knowledge provided at school, teachers are responsible for imparting social and emotional learning (Orchard, 2021a; Webster, 2021). Successful teachers in fostering character development should be able to develop an educational environment that encourages the growth of positive characters among students (Mohd Yusoff et al., 2022). Furthermore, they also become good examples for students to follow in their daily behaviour (Napratilora et al., 2021; Sanderse, 2013).

Parents, on the other hand, play a very vital role in developing adolescent character at home. More daily interactions on the part of parents and children offer opportunities to teach good morals (Moslehi et al., 2022). Really, along those lines of thought, the research also shows that parents could effectively strengthen and underpin their children's character education, which takes place in school (Ismail, 2018). With that, homes and schools must work cohesively together in terms of attention to adolescent character development (Zhu et al., 2022).

Despite the positive aspects, the relationship between parents and educators is not without difficulties. The most significant hindrance within character building revolves around the contrast of viewpoints between parents and teachers (Cankar et al., 2012). Furthermore, busy parents and time-poor teachers struggle to communicate effectively (Madsen & Madsen, 2022). It is, therefore, crucial to tackle these difficulties and improve collaboration between parents and teachers. Various mechanisms have been devised to strengthen the partnership, which is primarily centred around communication. This purpose requires open and frequent communication (Conus & Fahrni, 2019). The use of technology, such as the use of school communication apps, can facilitate better information exchange and coordination (See et al., 2020; Sianturi et al., 2023). In addition, organising joint activities such as workshops or seminars on character education can strengthen understanding and cooperation between teachers and parents (Šteh & Kalin, 2011).

These various strategies continue to support the realisation that good partnerships between teachers and parents significantly impact adolescent character development. Students who receive consistent support from teachers and parents tend to exhibit more positive behaviours and better academic performance (Epstein et al., 2009). They are also better able to cope with the challenges and pressures faced in everyday life (Schacter & Margolin, 2019). As such, this partnership is not only beneficial to character development but also to the overall well-being of students (Deng et al., 2018).

Several studies have been conducted to explore the partnership between teachers and parents in adolescent character development. The results show that this partnership can reduce negative behaviours and increase positive habits among adolescents. One study found that adolescents with parents actively involved in school activities had better discipline levels. Another study showed that effective cooperation can improve students' self-confidence and social skills.

Several studies have been conducted to explore the partnership between teachers and parents in adolescent character development. Among them, this partnership can reduce negative behaviours and increase positive habits among adolescents (Epstein et al., 2009); active involvement of parents in school activities influences the level of discipline for adolescents (Ismail, 2018); effective cooperation between teachers and parents can increase students' self-confidence and social skills (Wang et al., 2021).

Despite the many studies conducted, such a partnership has numerous dimensions that could benefit from further examination. Future research would also contribute to a better understanding of how culture, socio-economic conditions, and technology affect the relationship between the two. Besides, creating more efficient and reasonable partnership models is also crucial to guarantee that the character-building endeavour can be well-gained (Deng et al., 2018). Thus, the Systematic Literature Review analysis study in this area is important for the advancement of character education in the future. This study is expected to contribute as a rationale for developing a programme to strengthen the partnership between teachers and parents in fostering adolescent character.

Objectives of The Study

This study aims to analyse:

- 1) The efforts of parents and teachers in fostering adolescent character
- 2) Forms of partnership between teachers and parents in fostering teenagers' characters
- 3) Supporting and inhibiting factors in fostering adolescent character

Research Methods

This study used a qualitative approach with Systematic Literature Review (SLR) analysis. To get more comprehensive analysis results, it starts with creating research questions (Mohamed Shaffril et al., 2021). Then, the search is carried out by organising the criteria transparently (Lame, 2019) to limit systematic error (Higgins et al., 2011; Petticrew & Roberts, 2008). Next, the article search was conducted by identifying, selecting, and assessing then collecting, analysing, and synthesising published research literature related to teacher-parent partnerships in adolescent character development (Cook & West, 2012; Greenhalgh, 1997; Moher et al., 2009).

Search Strategy

Keyword searches on Scopus and ScienceDirect were conducted between February and July 2024, identifying 905 studies. The search term for the database was “(“Teacher-Parent”) AND (Collaboration OR Cooperation OR Partnership) AND (Moral OR Ethic OR Character)”

Inclusion and Exclusion Criteria

Inclusion and exclusion criteria were set for the 905 identified studies to ensure their relevance and appropriateness for analysis.

Table 1 Inclusion and Exclusion Criteria

	Inclusion Criteria	Exclusion Criteria
Publishing period	Published in 2018 – now (July 2024)	Published before 2018
Document Type	Research Article (Primer study: Qualitative, Quantitative, and Mixed Methods)	Secondary Study, Feature, news, correspondence, editorial, etc
Language	English and Indonesian	Other Than English and Indonesian
Population	Teacher-Parent	Other than Teacher-Parent
Intervention	Collaboration/Cooperation/Partnership	other than teacher and parent collaboration
Outcomes	Moral/Ethic/Character Education/Education/Coaching/Development for Adolescent	Research other than Moral/Ethic/Character Education/Education/Coaching/Development for Adolescent

Research Selection

Data Analysis

To make it easier to keep search result articles, the search results are then exported and saved to be managed with the Mendeley Reference Manager tool. Subsequently, the PRISMA framework technique is followed in the systematic review management process, which uses the Covidence web tool. Following the selection process based on the criteria, articles were extracted by classifying them by (a) author name, (b) year of publication,

(c) country, (d) title, and (e) results. Table 2 displays the features of the examined research.

Table 2 Characteristics of The Research Analysed

Research Question	Subtheme	Name and Year	Country	Research Results			
Teacher efforts in fostering adolescent character	The Teacher's Personality	Surikova & Fernández González, (2022)	Latvia, Northern Europe	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Joining teacher training in instilling adolescent's characters. 			
		Ariani et al., (2022)	Indonesia	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Enhancing teacher performance in collaborative modeling and habit strategies. 			
	Teacher with Parents	Ariani et al., (2022)	Ariani et al., (2022)	Indonesia	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> involving parents through exemplary methods and habituation build comprehensive social interaction 		
			Aziz et al., (2023)	Indonesia	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Educators convey essential messages about children and their learning development to their parents. Communicate with parents 		
			Ariani et al., (2022)	Indonesia	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Integrate all lessons by instilling values and morals 		
			Hart, (2023)	UK	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> conduct reflection communication with parents understand the situation and circumstances of parents at home be honest in communicating with parents 		
		(Liu et al., 2023)	United State	(Liu et al., 2023)	United State	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Teachers help monitor student behavior and quickly inform parents of any issues. 	
				Uswadin et al., (2019)	Indonesia	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Socialize character education implemented at school and invite habituation with parents. 	
				Teacher with adolescent	Hart, (2023)	UK	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> understand the student's situation and circumstances at home
						Indonesia	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Conceive of moral principles, embed them within the curriculum, and instill them through the establishment of whole school routines.

Parents' efforts in fostering adolescent character	Parents with Teachers	Liu et al., (2023)	United State	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Communicating with teachers about the child's behaviour Attend in-school activities that involve parents
	Parents with adolescent	Ariani et al., (2022)	Indonesia	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> directing, advising, and guiding children to be disciplined, independent, creative, obedient to worship, respectful to parents, and communicative in carrying out all activities and learning. communicative in carrying out all activities and learning
		Aziz et al., (2023)	Indonesia	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Let the older sister be in charge of the education and cultivation of the younger siblings. Using the facilities as they are Provide more time with children (quality time) setting an example for the child
		Liu et al., (2023)	United State	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> parents focus on responsibilities related to moral education responsible for disciplining and building character providing for financial needs and daily necessities. Monitor and review the child according to their capabilities and assist or find help for those who have difficulties with the homework. supportive in children's positive activities
Forms of teacher and parent partnerships in fostering adolescent characters		Ariani et al., (2022)	Indonesia	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Online learning and home visits
		Aziz et al., (2023)	Indonesia	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> building positive interactions between teachers and parents
		Harrison et al., (2022)	UK	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Shared understanding and goal setting
	-	Hart, (2023)	UK	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> parents and teachers together apply the same 'pressure' on students at home and school.
		Huda et al., (2022)	Indonesia, Turkey and Japan	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> The relationship between the school and parents is very important in

			understanding children's character.	
	Surikova & Fernández González, (2022)	Latvia, Northern Europe	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • regular meetings with parents and teachers, discussing children's achievements • regular individualized conversations and consultations between teachers and parents (for example, consultations, emails, messages, phone calls) • working together and understanding each other's values • meetings at home and school, handling difficult conversations, and communicating effectively • joint school/classroom events • interesting lectures and seminars, • social support. 	
	Uswadin et al., (2019)	Indonesia	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • shared responsibility between the principal, teachers, students, parents, and the community. 	
	Xie Fai Mar et al., (2023)	Canada	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • SMS to parents fill in the grade discussion worksheet. • Conducting discussions with parents • Understanding their role in the transfer process 	
Supporting factors for teacher and parent partnerships in fostering teenage characters	-	Ariani et al., (2022)	Indonesia	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • strong cooperation between teachers and parents • Direct some parenting responsibilities to the eldest child so that he can guide and help the younger ones develop their character.
	Harrison et al., (2022)	UK	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • parents and teachers have similar priorities, both prioritize character over achievement and rank moral virtues such as compassion and honesty highly 	
	Liu et al., (2023)	United State	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • parents talk with teachers to ensure to children's 	

				<ul style="list-style-type: none"> behavior and will report problems without delay there is a division of labor between parents and teachers in the child's education.
Factors Inhibiting teacher-parent Partnerships in Youth Character Development	Teacher Obstacles	Ariani et al., (2022)	Indonesia	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> inability to master learning technology interactive learning is not optimal difficult to communicate with parents
		Aziz et al., (2023)	Indonesia	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> communication due to media limitations parents' lack of understanding of teacher expectations inadequate infrastructure and lack of readiness for online learning.
		Harrison et al., (2022)	UK	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> teachers misperceive parents' priorities
		Surikova & Fernández González, (2022)	Latvia, Northern Europe	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> negative parental attitudes (e.g., arrogance, apathy, lack of interest and responsibility); lack of parental time and energy, heavy workload; and unsupportive family climate and culture (moral norms, values, virtues).
		Xie Fai Mar et al., (2023)	Canada	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> large additional workload a large number of classes and students to handle playing a secondary role in the school inadequate time.
Parents Obstacles		Ariani et al., (2022)	Indonesia	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> time management between duties and work lack of interaction and communication. parents' ignorance in using learning technologies difficulty communicating with teachers
		Aziz et al., (2023)	Indonesia	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Limited facilities Busy parents Difficulty in parenting Parents who cite their lack of education as thought-provoking.
		Harrison et al., (2022)	UK	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> parents misperceive teachers' priorities
		Ariani et al., (2022)	Indonesia	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> cost unstable internet signal

Barriers of both or the other	Harrison et al., (2022)	UK	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • unsupportive facilities and infrastructure • parents and teachers prioritize academic achievement over character. • teachers and parents do not communicate their educational priorities
	Hart, (2023)	UK	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • boundaries at school that seek to influence practices and values at home.
	Xie Fai Mar et al., (2023)	Canada	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • neglect teaching values because of the overemphasis on academic results.

Results and Discussion

Teacher's Efforts in Developing Adolescent Character

Based on the synthesis of data that has been carried out in the literature review regarding teacher efforts in fostering adolescent character, a clearer explanation can be seen in the following chart:

Picture 1: Teachers' effort scheme in the character development of adolescents

The findings indicate that the teacher's role in adolescent character-building is comprehensive and complex. In foreign countries, teachers participate in self-improvement by internalising these values in the educational process and being role models for the students. In Indonesia, 'character' development is defined as achieving an ideal grade for the teacher. Overseas, teachers focus on the principles of character education, supervision of the pupils, and the overall promotion of a morally conducive atmosphere. On the other hand, in Indonesia, strategies like moral education-learning partnerships and moral education-moral curriculum integration are prominently used. But also, the teachers act as role models and advise students and visit students' families to learn about their circumstances. This is in agreement with research by Napratilora et al., (2021) where it is noted that teachers are, in all aspects, bearers of ideas, attitudes, and character, of course, the students will welcome the teacher's proposed views and put them into practice later in their lives.

Teachers are often seen as models for character education. However, they are infrequently observed demonstrating the values, and as a result, few students consider them worthy of imitation (Sanderse, 2013). In this regard, teachers are confronted with a challenge concerning the moral growth of the students (Mohd Yusoff et al., 2022). Teachers must focus on some troublesome maladaptive behaviours that stem from stress and are exhibited by students in school settings (Narvaez, 2021). It has been stressed that the success of character education is a professional endeavour of all teachers since their personal convictions and way of life principles tend to impart on a child's character thus, the child models how society regards desirable behaviour (Bergem, 1990; Lumpkin, 2008).

In general, teachers' struggles in youth character development were indicative of efforts to meet the requirements of the given cultural environment. This corresponds with the findings by Stafford (1987) of family-pronged research that teachers must know themselves well enough, especially to know the family background of every learner and even parents of all sorts of learners with love, acceptance, and commendation. Thus, teachers' efforts lay the foundation upon which successful and sustainable character development among adolescents can be nurtured in an integrated manner alongside personal growth, character education, collaboration with parents, and school facilities.

Parent's Efforts in Developing Adolescent Character

Based on the synthesis of data that has been carried out in the systematic review regarding parent's efforts in fostering adolescent character, a clearer explanation can be seen in the following chart:

Picture 2 Scheme of parental efforts in character development of adolescents

Parental contribution to the development of adolescent character in other countries as well as Indonesia includes an active intervention aimed at assisting students as well as teachers. In other countries, the involvement of parents encompasses the provision of moral training, providing for children's needs, tracking growth, as well as endorsing school programmes. Mothering is generally directed towards the physical, social, and spiritual nurturing of the child, placing great emphasis on the relevance of engagement in cultural affairs to the educational process (Liu et al., 2023).

In Indonesia, decisions, principles, and adult behaviours, including embracing corporate worship, impact child nurturing. In addition, they impart supporting tools,

practise honesty and good morals, and assign older children guiding roles. Good and adequate relations, monitoring of progress, motivation, and punishment for bad actions all form part of this task.

Regarding adolescent character development, exposure to parental efforts has taught that family education, that is, the interaction between parents and children, is reciprocal and complementary (Wang et al., 2022). Children and adolescents are influenced by their parents' roles and behaviour (Berglund et al., 2022). Teachers and parents have a similar responsibility over the children's character building. The difference is that teachers do it within a formal system, whereas parents do it within the informal system at home (Seymour, 1972). The two are not dichotomous but rather a continuum that supplements one another in a learning situation (Folkestad, 2006). Because of that, parent-teacher partnerships should be complimentary at home and in school, concentrating on the best interests of the students as agreed by both parties.

Abroad, this type of partnership is expressed in communication as well as in parental attendance to school activities when teachers make suggestions and parents engage in conversations (Liu et al., 2023). In Indonesia, the same concept has been adopted through social interactions, reporting to invite teachers and willing to participate in the activities organised by the school (Ariani et al., 2022; Liu et al., 2023).

Forms of Teacher-Parent Partnership in Adolescent Character Development

Various forms of teacher-parent partnerships in character development in various literatures are as shown in the following chart:

Picture 3 Partnership scheme between teachers and parents in character development for adolescents

As formed during the development of the educational programme, the bond created between society and school as a joint venture in moral instruction of youth differs from that in some countries, for instance, Indonesia, in terms of more emphasis on the value characters of the adolescent. In some other countries, the partnership includes regular meetings or more indirect contact through media such as WAG, e-mails, or the telephone. As the report suggests, partnerships include components such as defining common goals, individual conversations, and presence at the school, as well as pedagogical work with an accent on interaction and control over the family-level conditions at which a child's development occurs. Stafford (1987) emphasises the significance of parents as the first educators and the importance of direct communication about children's academic

progress and children's needs while Kraft and Dougherty (2013) argue that children's achievement can also be as a result of advice provided by teachers.

In the context of Indonesia, the boundaries of the partnerships also include bridging face-to-face interactions, learning from home, and role visits. It emphasises on the need for teachers, parents, and children themselves to assist in averting undesirable behaviour and educate the children's character values through supervision and punishment measures. As outlined in the report, this partnership is manifested through parent-teacher meetings, parents teaching in class, parent-teacher communication and educational tours for children in the last grade. Communication occurs both in direct and indirect forms through the phone, WA, and messenger books, ensuring that there is a shared effort to promote adolescent character.

In Indonesia, parent-teacher partnerships are growing stronger through parent-teacher meetings, some moral socialisation programmes, and setting up parents' and students' support centres. Teachers communicate well with parents and build on their trust and understanding of their backgrounds and characteristics. This partnership is multifaceted from different communications, as observed by Sunata (2023), who explains the role of communication in social changes.

Though the approaches in parent-teacher partnerships vary from the country, the partnerships still support moral development for adolescents. The two parties come together for the best outcome (Daheri et al., 2023), consistent with *ta'awun* in Islam, which is to offer help in the interest of students (Sarifudin et al., 2023).

Supporting Factors of Teacher-Parent Partnership in Adolescent Character Development

Based on the results of the data synthesis that has been carried out in the systematic review, it can be seen more clearly in the following chart:

Picture 4 Scheme of supporting factors for teacher and parent partnerships in character development for adolescents

From the findings of data synthesis in the systematic review on supporting factors for teacher-parent partnerships in adolescent character development, some conclusions can also be made. First, common priorities in moral education between teachers and parents are quite crucial. The character development of children becomes more efficient and general when both parties have similar focal targets, as in the case in (Epstein et al., 2009). In addition, conflict can be minimised, and cooperation maximised if a division of responsibilities between teachers and parents has been clearly articulated (Hornby & Lafaele, 2011). Another secondary factor that must be acknowledged is parents' efforts to reach out to the teachers. Such parents can meet the child's requirements at school and adjust these in their home environment, reinforcing this partnership (Hoover-Dempsey & Sandler, 1997).

Yanti and Marzuki (2021) emphasise that in the case of Indonesia, effective character education of students can only be achieved when teachers and parents actively collaborate. From there, parents practise what they preach, namely by having their eldest kids assist the younger ones, making learning less isolating and more friendly. These factors promote the effectiveness of character education programmes in, say, Indonesia and other countries, although the focus and the context are different.

Inhibiting Factors of Teacher-Parent Partnership in Adolescent Character Development

The synthesis of systemic review data leads us to conclude that among the factors that prevent the establishment of teacher-parent cooperation in character building of adolescent children in foreign countries are the misconceptions, negative parental attitudes (such as arrogance, apathy, and lack of interest), cultural variation between parents and families, excessive burden of teachers, multiphase classes and students, and time constraints. In Indonesia, there are also barriers such as the lack of skill in handling technology, non-optimal interactive learning processes, low infrastructure and facility standards, and irene’s parents.

Barriers for parents abroad include misperceptions and lack of communication with teachers, while in Indonesia, the challenges are time management, lack of interaction, ignorance of technology, and limited facilities and communication. In addition, overseas, teachers and parents often choose academics without communicating about educational priorities, while in Indonesia the barriers are related to costs, internet signals, and facilities. For more clarity on the factors inhibiting teacher-parent partnerships in character development, see the following scheme:

Picture 5 Scheme of inhibiting factors of teacher and parent partnership in the character development of adolescents

The various obstacles teachers and parents face make the condition of students or adolescents found to be in an unclear position. This is because families and schools shift responsibility for educating students to each other (Tufekčić, 2015). Parents do not understand and have little provision in education and child care, especially in character education. The level of parental education is a significant predictor of parenting knowledge for parents (Bornstein et al., 2010). So that students cannot only get character education from teachers alone (Orchard, 2021b) Cooperation is needed between both parties because both are interconnected and have strong relationships with each other. Good cooperation between parents and schools must exist so that there are no mistakes in implementing education. To do things well, the partnership between parents and schools must be in the same direction and in harmony based on mutually agreed-upon interests in dealing with students.

This research aims to enrich the scientific literature by providing a comprehensive perspective on cooperation between teachers and parents in fostering adolescent character. This is very important to provide a more holistic, critical, and harmonious

understanding in fostering a cooperative relationship between teachers and parents, especially in fostering adolescent character.

Conclusion

Teachers' and parents and parents' growth of adolescent character are multisectoral in scope abroad and in Indonesia. Models overseas have other specialisations which employ them to provide individual development within the educational process. In the case of Indonesia, the teachers do character education by combining lesson teachings with pupil home visits. It is important also to regard professionalism and modelling as a teacher. Parents also contribute to the adolescent character by attending school functions, offering moral support and characterising their children. In Indonesia, involving the eldest children in household chores is an established norm. A teacher-parent partnership is very productive in accomplishing aims. Prominent enabling factors are emphasis on the issues of morality education, understanding division of load, and parents' involvement. In Indonesia, cooperation with the slackoff delegation of the eldest son is productive. Obstacles that should be addressed include misconceptions, negative behaviour patterns, workload and technological barriers. Both parents and teachers have important responsibilities in ensuring an efficient character development process for adolescents by using the enabling factors while avoiding obstacles. On the other hand, the future directions for this study are to expand the coverage and scope of the study in order to foster more significant potential in its impact.

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